

Duct-vented hydrogen–air deflagrations: the effect of duct length and hydrogen concentration

Fuqiang Yang ^a, Jin guo ^{a,b,*}, Changjian Wang ^{c,d}, Shoucxiang Lu ^{b,*}

^a *College of Environment and Resources, Fuzhou University, Fuzhou 350116, PR China*

^b *State Key Laboratory of Fire Science, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei 230027, PR China*

^c *School of Civil Engineering, Hefei University of Technology, Hefei 230009, PR China*

^d *Anhui's International Joint Research Center on Hydrogen Safety, Hefei, 230009, China*

Corresponding Author

Jin Guo guojin@fzu.edu.cn

College of Environment and Resources, Fuzhou University, Fuzhou, Fujian 350116, PR China

Shoucxiang Lu sxlu@ustc.edu.cn

State Key Laboratory of Fire Science, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, Anhui 230027, PR China

Abstract: Experiments on duct-vented explosions of hydrogen–air mixtures in a 12.3 l cylindrical vessel were conducted, and the effects of duct length and hydrogen concentration on the maximum overpressure and flame behavior within and outside the vented enclosure were investigated. The results show that the maximum overpressure in the vessel first increased and then was maintained nearly unchanged with the length of a relief duct increasing to 2 m. For a given duct length, the maximum overpressure first increased and then decreased when hydrogen concentration increased from 20% to 55%. The burn-up in the duct caused the gas mixtures to move in reverse from the duct to vessel, which consequently decreased the venting efficiency. A pressure wave caused by burn-up in the duct was observed, which resulted in a pressure peak in the external pressure–time histories after it traveled outside the duct. The maximum external overpressure first increased and then decreased with an increase in duct length. For a given duct length, the maximum external overpressure increased with an increase in hydrogen concentration.

Keywords: Vented explosion; Duct length; Hydrogen; Overpressure; Flame; Pressure wave

1. Introduction

Explosion venting is widely used to protect equipment from accidental internal gaseous explosions. For enclosures located inside buildings, relief ducts are recommended both in EN14994 [1] and NFPA68 [2] to discharge hot products, flames, or shock waves to the outdoors.

Duct-vented hydrocarbon–air mixtures have been investigated extensively [3-8], and it has been reported that duct length is one of the most important factors affecting the explosion venting process [9-14]. Experiments on explosion venting of 9.5% methane–air mixtures through ducts with length of 10.5, 30, and 50 *cm* were performed in two cubical explosion vessels with side of 18 and 38 *cm* by McCann et al. [9]. Their experimental results confirmed that the pressure oscillations with low frequency occurred shortly after vent failure were Helmholtz type which arises from the bulk motion of the flame bubble towards and away from the vent [9], and the maximum reduced overpressure was higher than that in a simple vented explosion without a duct. Kordylewski and Wach [10] conducted vented town gas–air explosion tests in a 22 *l* spherical vessel with duct length ranging from 0 to 2 *m*. They found that the maximum overpressure did not increase monotonically with the increase of duct length. DeGood and Chatrathi [11] discovered that the use of a 1-*m*-long duct resulted in slightly lower maximum overpressure in a 2.6 *m*³ cylindrical vessel compared with simple venting. Ponizy and Leyer [12] performed explosion tests in a duct-vented cylinder 0.4 *m* in length and 0.108 *m* in internal diameter. Different from most previous research, both the vessel and the duct in their experiments were filled with combustible mixtures before ignition. Their experimental results showed that the maximum overpressure increased when duct length increased from 0.6 to 2.6 *m*. The effect of a relief duct with length ranging from 1.8 to 25 *m* on vented stoichiometric acetone vapor–air deflagrations in vessels up to 10 *m*³ was investigated by Molkov et al. [13]. However, it appeared to be difficult to obtain the relationship between the maximum reduced overpressure and the duct length owing to the variation in the vent burst pressure.

It has been found that frictional loss of the outflow and inertia of the gas column in the duct, Helmholtz oscillations in

the vessel, and burn-up in the duct are responsible for the effects of ducts on explosion venting [10,12,14,15]. The results of numerical investigations have demonstrated that burn-up in the duct is the dominant factor resulting in higher severity of duct-vented explosions [16,17], and the conclusion has been confirmed by experimental results [18-20].

Although duct-vented explosions of hydrocarbons have been extensively investigated, little work has been conducted on hydrogen–air mixtures, which is more reactive and prone to transit from deflagration to detonation under suitable conditions [21-23]. Kasmani [21] performed experiments on vented hydrogen–air mixtures in a 0.5-*m*-diameter cylindrical vessel with a 0.162-*m*-diameter duct connected; both the vessel and the duct were 1 *m* long. They found that hydrogen-air mixtures behaved differently with low burning gases such as methane-air mixture, and detonation was observed for 16% hydrogen–air mixtures ignited at the center of the cylindrical vessel. Kumar et al. [24] conducted experiments on explosion venting of 8.5%–20% hydrogen–air mixtures in 2.3-*m* diameter spherical vessel with a 3-*m*-long duct connected. In their experiments, the vent cover was located at the end of the duct; that is, both the vessel and duct were filled with hydrogen–air mixtures. It was found that explosion overpressure increased with an increase in hydrogen concentration. Vented explosion of hydrogen–air mixtures through a 0.5-*m*-long duct was investigated and it was found that the use of the relief duct significantly increased the explosion overpressure compared with the cases without the duct for hydrogen concentration ranging from lean to rich [25]. The experiments on explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures from a 1.5-*m*-long duct to a vented cylindrical vessel showed that maximum reduced overpressure first increased and then decreased with an increase in hydrogen concentration [26].

Apart from the previous investigations on duct-vented explosion of hydrogen-air mixtures [21,24,25], one of the most important issue has not been studied yet: how does the length of relief duct affect explosion venting? Because in the previous research [21,24,25], relief ducts with fixed length were used. To answer the question, relief ducts of different length were used in this study to investigate the pressure buildup and flow field within and outside the vented enclosure during explosion venting of hydrogen–air mixtures with concentration ranging from 20% to 55%.

2. Experimental

Fig.1 shows the test enclosure. The venting enclosure consisted of a 12.3 l cylindrical vessel and relief ducts 7×7 cm in cross-section with different lengths. Details of the test enclosure can be found in our previous study [25]. The flame images in the vessel and duct were captured by a high-speed Schlieren system at a frequency of 30000 Hz. Three pressure sensors, PS1–PS3, as shown in Fig. 2, were employed to record the pressure–time histories in the vessel, duct, and the exterior. These sensors were mounted on the vessel wall, on the duct wall 40 cm from the vent cover, and 60 cm from the exit of the relief duct, respectively.

Fig.1. Test enclosure.

A piece of paper was fitted between the relief duct and one of the vessel necks to simulate vent cover with relatively low activation pressures. Relief ducts with lengths of 0 (without the duct), 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and 2 m were used to investigate the effect of duct length on the explosion venting process; the dimensionless duct length (L/D), where L and D were duct length and duct width respectively, was 0, 7.1, 14.3, 21.4 and 28.6. Hydrogen–air mixtures with concentration ranging from 20% to 55%, prepared according to Dalton law of partial pressure, were considered. Ignition was performed by an electric spark generated by an ignition plug. All tests were performed at 100-kPa initial pressure and 280 K temperature.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of experimental layout. PS₁–PS₃ are the pressure sensors.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of duct length on internal overpressure

Typical pressure–time histories are presented in Fig. 3. Transient higher overpressure in the duct than that in the vessel ($PS_2 > PS_1$), as shown in Fig.3(a), was observed in all tests with ducts. This phenomenon has been confirmed in previous research to be caused by burn-up in the duct [16,20]. Concretely, when the vent cover was opened, the flame was still far from vent as shown in Fig. 4(a); therefore, unburned hydrogen–air mixtures were first vented and mixed turbulently with the air in the duct to form combustible gas mixtures with high turbulence levels. The violent burn-up in the duct was triggered when the flame propagated into the duct as shown in Fig.4(b), and transient higher overpressure in the duct was reached as a result [8,16, 25]. After that, the overpressure in vessel increased continuously to its maximum value and then decreased.

Fig. 3. Typical pressure–time histories.

The use of a duct has been shown to result in gas mixtures moving in reverse from the duct to the vessel owing to transient higher overpressure in the duct than that in vessel [8,12,18, 25]. This reverse flow was observed in all current

tests with a duct, as shown in Fig. 4(c) and (d). With an increase in internal overpressure, the reverse flow was pushed outside the vessel ultimately as shown in Fig.4(e). For hydrogen–air mixtures with a given concentration, the duration of the reverse flow increased with an increase in L/D from 7.1 to 14.3 and remained nearly unchanged with a further increase in L/D . In the tests without a duct, reverse flow with very short duration, owing to external explosion, was observed for the current 55% hydrogen–air mixtures and for the 67.8% hydrogen–air mixtures in our previous research [27].

Fig. 4. Schlieren flame images in the vessel with 30% H_2 and $L/D=14.3$.

Fig.5 summarizes the relationship between the maximum overpressure in the vessel as a function of L/D and hydrogen concentration. For 20% hydrogen-air mixtures, Fig.5 shows that duct length has no apparent effect on the maximum reduced overpressure due to its slow burning rate. However, for hydrogen concentration ranging from 25% to 55%, the maximum overpressure increased quickly with an increase in L/D to 14.3, which is attributed mainly to the turbulent burn-up in the duct [16-20]. Fig. 5 also shows that the length effect of the relief duct on the maximum reduced overpressure was not significant when the L/D exceeded 14.3; similar trends were reported by Kordylewski and Wach [10] and Ferrara et al. [16]. One reason may be that the duration of the reverse flow was kept nearly unchanged for $L/D > 14.3$; thus, the blockage of venting by the reverse flow is also nearly independent of L/D .

Fig. 5. Maximum reduced overpressure versus L/D.

Moreover, Fig. 5 shows that the maximum overpressure for a given L/D first increased and then decreased when hydrogen concentration increased from 20% to 55%, that is because the burning rate of hydrogen–air mixtures first increases and then decreases with an increase in hydrogen concentration from lean to rich [28].

3.2 Flame propagation in vessel and duct

Fig. 6 compares the average flame speed, which, calculated from the flame images, is the ratio of the distance the flame front travels between two frames to the time interval ($1/30000$ s), for a 30% hydrogen–air mixture in the cases with and without a 1-*m*-long duct. The use of a relief duct had no apparent effect on the early stage of explosion venting, and flame spread at an oscillatory speed of approximately 14–26 *m/s* in the two cases. When the flame approached the vent, the average flame speed significantly increased owing to the venting of unburned gases before the flame. Fig. 6 shows that the average flame speed in the case with a relief duct was lower than that without the duct shortly before the flame entered the neck of the vessel. This result is attributed to reduction in the venting flow rate caused by the duct gas column inertia and frictional losses in the duct [10,12].

Fig. 6. Average flame speed in the vessel with 30% H₂.

The flame was further accelerated after it entered the duct. As shown in Fig. 7 (a), the average flame speed nearly doubled when the flame travelled from approximately 16 to 38 cm downstream the vent cover; the increase in flame speed was oscillatory rather than monotonic. After a period of acceleration, the flame speed did not increase again. As shown in Fig.7(b), when the flame moved approximately 120 cm downstream the vent cover, it propagated at an oscillatory speed from approximately 510 to 610 m/s.

Fig. 7. Average flame speed in duct vs. distance from vent cover (30% H₂, L/D=21.4).

For hydrogen concentration equal to and greater than 25%, pressure waves (PW) were observed in relief ducts, as shown in Fig. 8. Pressure wave 1 (PW1) as shown in Fig.8(a) resulted from the burst of the vent cover, and pressure wave 2 (PW2) in Fig.8(b) was caused by the burn-up and flame acceleration in the duct. PW1 and PW2 travelled at approximately 370 and 780 m/s, respectively. Fig. 8(b) and (c) show that PW2 detached from the unburned gas mixtures

owing to its higher speed. Shortly after PW2 passed, a flame with an oscillatory high speed followed, as discussed above. It can also be deduced from Fig.8 that the unburned gas that enters the vent duct after the vent cover opens will be diluted with the air in the duct and becomes leaner when it rushes outside of duct to the exterior, and as a result the external pressure-time histories will have close relationship with initial hydrogen concentration as will be discussed in the next section.

Fig. 8. Typical flow field in the duct with 30% H₂ and L/D=14.3. PW-pressure wave.

3.3 External pressure–time histories

Two pressure peaks in the external pressure–time histories were distinguished in most duct-vented explosions, as shown in Fig. 9(a). The pressure peaks were closely related to the external flow field. As shown in Fig. 10(a), after the vent cover was opened, the air in the duct was first pushed out due to the venting of gases from the vessel, and a mushroom-like cloud formed in front of the duct exit. Then, pressure wave 3 (PW3) appeared and resulted in the first pressure peak (p_1), and PW3 is actually the pressure wave, which resulted from burn-up in the duct (PW2 in Fig.8), rushed outside the duct. Unburned gas mixtures following PW3 were vented as shown in Fig 10(b) and (c), and a combustible gas cloud that formed in the exterior was ignited by the vented flame to result in pressure wave 4 (PW4) shown in Fig.10(d) and consequently the second pressure peak [29-33].

Fig. 9. Typical external pressure–time histories with 45% H₂.

Fig. 10. Typical external flow field (45% H₂, L/D=14.3). PW-pressure wave.

In the tests without the duct, only one dominant pressure peak was measured in the external pressure–time histories, as shown in Fig. 9 (b). Similar to the second pressure peak in the tests with the duct, this pressure peak was also caused by the external explosion. Compared with duct-vented explosions, the unburned hydrogen–air mixtures were vented at much lower speed in the tests without the duct, and a combustible cloud formed near the vent as shown in Fig.11(a). When the combustible cloud was ignited, a nearly spherical PW4 formed, as shown in Fig.11(b), which resulted in the only dominant pressure peak in the external pressure–time histories.

Fig. 11. Pressure wave caused by external explosion in the case L/D=0 at 45% H₂. PW- pressure wave.

The relationship between maximum external overpressure and L/D is presented in Fig. 12. In the tests with the relief duct, the higher one of the two pressure peaks was defined as the maximum external overpressure. For 20% hydrogen–air mixtures, the maximum external overpressure was very low, which is attributed to the very weak burn-up in the duct and

external explosion. For a given L/D , Fig. 12 shows that the maximum external overpressure increased nearly monotonically with an increase in hydrogen concentration from 20% to 55%, and it should be pointed out that the trend was different from that of the maximum internal overpressure as shown in Fig.5. As discussed above, the maximum external overpressure was due to either PW3 or PW4, which has close relationship with the diluted hydrogen-air mixture in the duct and the exterior, respectively. It can be deduced that the initially very rich gases, for example 55% hydrogen-air mixtures in current experiments, will be diluted to a certain concentration which results in the highest external explosion overpressure for a given duct length.

Fig. 12. Maximum external overpressure versus L/D .

Regarding the effect of L/D , Fig. 12 shows that the maximum external overpressure first increased and then decreased with an increase in L/D from 0 (without the duct) to 28.6, and the turning points of the trend depended on the hydrogen concentration. Compared with the tests without the duct, the first increase in the maximum external overpressure in the tests with a short duct was caused mainly by the pressure wave generated by the burn-up in the duct (PW2 in Fig. 8 and PW3 in Fig. 10). This resulted in the first pressure peak in the external pressure–time histories, as discussed above. However, the magnitude of the pressure peaks decreased with further increases in L/D because the magnitude of the first pressure peak p_1 decreased owing to attenuation of PW2 when it traveled a longer distance. Alternatively, this may be attributed to the decreased magnitude of the second pressure peak p_2 . Because the ratio between the duct to the volume of the vessel increases as the increase in L/D , resultantly larger amounts of unburned hydrogen–air mixtures were consumed

in the duct [34] and less was vented to the exterior to form the external combustible cloud; thus, the intensity of the external explosion decreased.

4. Conclusions

Explosion venting of 20%-55% hydrogen–air mixtures through a relief duct with dimensionless duct length (L/D) ranging from 0 (without the duct) to 28.6 was experimentally investigated.

Reverse flow owing to the burn-up in the duct was observed in all tests with a duct, which decreased the efficiency of explosion venting. The maximum reduced overpressure in the vessel increased with an increase in L/D to 14.3; further increases in L/D has no apparent effect. The maximum reduced overpressure first increased and then decreased with an increase in hydrogen concentration from 20% to 55%.

The flame was significantly accelerated in the duct. Pressure waves caused by the burn-up in the duct were observed that traveled outside the duct to result in one of two pressure peaks in duct-vented explosions; the other peak was caused by the external explosion occurring in the exterior.

The maximum external overpressure increased monotonically with an increase in hydrogen concentration, and it first increased and then decreased with an increase in L/D .

Acknowledgments

This study is supported by the National Key Research and Development Program of China (No. 2016YFE0113400), HySEA Project through the European Commission's "Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking (Grant no.671461), the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No.51741402), and the Open Fund of State Key Laboratory of Fire Science of China (No. HZ2017-KF04).

References

- [1] EN 14994. Gas explosion venting protective systems. Brussels: European Standard, 2007.
- [2] NFPA68. Standard on Explosion Protection by Deflagration Venting. Quincy, MA: National Fire Protection

Association, 2013 Edition.

[3] Iida N, Kawaguchi O, Sato GT. Premixed flame propagating into a narrow channel at a high speed, part 1: Flame behaviors in the channel. *Combustion and Flame*, 1985, 60(3): 245-255.

[4] Kasmani RM, Andrews GE, Phylaktou HN, Willacy SK. Influence of static burst pressure and ignition position on duct-vented gas explosions. In: *Proceedings of the 5th International Seminar on Fire and Explosion Hazards*, Edinburgh, UK, 2007.

[5] Ponizy B, Veysiere B. Mitigation of explosions in a vented vessel connected to a duct. *Combustion Science and Technology*, 2000, 158(1): 167-182.

[6] Ferrara G, Willacy SK, Phylaktou HN, Andrews GE, Benedetto AD, MkPadi MC. Duct-vented propane-air explosions with central and rear ignition. In: *Proceedings of the 8th International Association for Fire Safety Science (IAFSS) Symposium*, Beijing, 2005.

[7] Kasmani RM, Andrews GE, Phylaktou HN. Experimental study on vented gas explosion in a cylindrical vessel with a vent duct. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 2013, 91(4): 245-252.

[8] Ponizy B, Hennenon N, Claverie A, Veysiere B. Detailed investigation of flame transmission from a vessel to a discharge duct. *Combustion and Flame*, 2014, 161 (5): 1348-1364.

[9] McCann DPJ, Thomas GO, Edwards DH. Gasdynamics of vented explosions part 1: Experimental studies. *Combustion and Flame*, 1985, 59(3): 233-250.

[10] Kordylewski W, Wach J. Influence of ducting on explosion pressure: Small scale experiments. *Combustion and Flame*, 1988, 71(1):51-61.

[11] Degood R, Chatrathi K. Comparative analysis of test work studying factors influencing pressures developed in vented deflagrations. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 1991, 4(5): 297-304.

[12] Ponizy B, Leyer JC. Flame dynamics in a vented vessel connected to a duct: 1. Mechanism of vessel-duct

interaction. *Combustion and Flame*, 1999, 116(1-2): 259-271.

[13] Molkov V, Baratov A, Korolchenko A. Dynamics of gas explosions in vented vessels: a critical review and progress. *Progress in Astronautics and Aeronautics*, 1993, 154: 117-131.

[14] Russo P, Benedetto AD. Effects of a duct on the venting of explosions—Critical review. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 2007, 85(1): 9-22.

[15] Ural EA. A simplified method for predicting the effect of ducts connected to explosion vents. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 1993, 6(1): 3-10.

[16] Ferrara G, Benedetto AD, Salzano E, Russo G. CFD analysis of gas explosions vented through relief pipes. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2006, 137(2): 654-665.

[17] Tang P, Jiang J. Numerical Simulation of Duct-vented Gas Explosion. *Procedia Engineering*, 2011, 18(18): 25-30.

[18] Ponizy B, Leyer JC. Flame dynamics in a vented vessel connected to a duct: 2. Influence of ignition site, membrane rupture, and turbulence. *Combustion and Flame*, 1999, 116(1-2): 272-281.

[19] Molkov V. Venting of deflagrations: dynamics of the process in systems with a duct and receiver. In: *Proceedings of the fourth international symposium on fire safety science*. Ottawa, Canada, 1994.

[20] Ferrara G, Willacy SK, Phylaktou HN, Andrews GE, Di Benedetto A, Salzano E, Russo G. Venting of gas explosion through relief ducts: Interaction between internal and external explosions. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2008, 115(1-2): 358-368.

[21] Kasmani RM. Vented gas explosions. Diss. University of Leeds, 2008.

[22] Medvedev SP, Polenov AN, Khomik SV, Gelfand BE. Initiation of upstream-directed detonation induced by the venting of gaseous explosion. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 1994; 25(1): 73-78.

[23] Dorofeev SB, Bezmelnitsin AV, Sidorov VP. Transition to detonation in vented hydrogen–air explosions. *Combustion and Flame* 1995; 103(3): 243-246.

- [24] Kumar RK, Dewit WA, Greig DR. Vented explosion of hydrogen–air mixtures in a large volume. *Combustion Science and Technology*, 1989, 66(4-6): 251-266.
- [25] Guo J, Wang CJ, Liu XY. Experimental study on duct-vented explosion of hydrogen–air mixtures in a wide range of equivalence ratio. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 2016, 55(35): 9518-9523.
- [26] Li HW, Guo J, Yang FQ, Wang CJ, Zhang JQ, Lu SX. Explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures from a duct to a vented vessel. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 2018, 43(24): 11307-11313.
- [27] Guo J, Sun XX, Rui SC, Cao Y, Hu KL, Wang CJ. Effect of ignition position on vented hydrogen–air explosions. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 2015, 40(45): 15780-15788.
- [28] Dahoe AE. Laminar burning velocities of hydrogen–air mixtures from closed vessel gas explosions. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 2005, 18(3): 152-166.
- [29] Chen ZH, Fan BC, Jiang XH, Ye JF. Investigations of secondary explosions induced by venting. *Process Safety Progress*, 2006, 25(3): 255-261.
- [30] Harrison AJ, Eyre JA. External explosions” as a result of explosion venting. *Combustion Science and Technology* 1987, 52(1-3): 91-106.
- [31] Proust Ch, Leprette E. The dynamics of vented gas explosions. *Process Safety Progress*, 2010, 29(3): 231-235.
- [32] Tomlin G, Johnson DM, Cronin P, Phylaktou HN, Andrews GE. The effect of vent size and congestion in large-scale vented natural gas/air explosions. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 2015, 35:169-181.
- [33] Kuznetsov M, Friedrich A, Stern G, Kotchourko N, Jallais S, L’Hostis B. Medium-scale experiments on vented hydrogen deflagration. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 2015, 36: 416-428.
- [34] Lunn G, Crowhurst D, Hey M. The effect of vent ducts on the reduced explosion pressures of vented dust explosions. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 1988, 1(4): 182-196.